

OVERCOMING BARRIERS TO LEARNING HAZOP VIA THE USE OF DYNAMIC SIMULATION

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Abstract

HAZOP (Hazard and Operability Studies) is an important tool in the study of chemical process plant safety and loss prevention, and formed a key component in the education of chemical engineers. A major problem faced by educators in the teaching of HAZOP is the lack of practical real-world experience among students. The traditional way of teaching HAZOP often resulted in students failing to cover all aspects of a possible process plant upset. For safety reasons, there is also no practical way, in an academic setting such as in a laboratory or workshop, to provide students with the required experience in handling various process plant upsets for example high temperature or excessive over-pressure. This paper details the preliminary results of an initiative, based on the Kolb Learning Cycle, to help student overcome the barriers in learning HAZOP, through the use of a commercially available dynamic simulation training software. The lessons learnt from the initiative and suggested action plans are discussed.

Keywords: *Dynamic simulation, chemical engineering, Kolb's Learning Cycle, HAZOP*

Introduction: What is HAZOP?

HAZOP stands for Hazard and Operability Studies. It is a method widely used in the chemical processing industries for identifying hazards and problems which prevented efficient operation. It is a technique which provides opportunities for people to let their imaginations go free and think of all possible ways in which hazards or operating problems might arise, but done in a systematic way (Kletz, 1999). A HAZOP study is generally led by a HAZOP Team Leader: someone who is qualified to lead these studies by nature of his/her training and experience, especially process troubleshooting. The rest of the HAZOP team members comprises a multi-disciplinary mix of process design and engineering, project engineering and management, maintenance and inspection, operations, safety, and environmental personnel familiar with the process under study.

In a HAZOP process, the team work uses a series of "guide words" to help them identify possible deviations of various plant operating conditions (such as flow rate,

temperature, pressure, liquid level, etc) from their intended steady-state behavior, i.e. a stable operation. For example, by combining the guide word NO with the operating variable FLOW, one gets a deviation of NO FLOW. The team then brainstorms for possible causes that can lead to a NO FLOW condition, and the identify plausible consequences that may result from a NO FLOW condition. The process is repeated many times using other combinations of guide words and operating variables until the entire chemical process plant operation is completely covered.

Practically all safety courses in any respectable chemical engineering program will feature the teaching of HAZOP. Students from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering in Singapore Polytechnic are no exception. They are required to complete a 45-hour core module entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*, out of which 6 hours are dedicated to the teaching of HAZOP. The module is non-examinable, i.e. students are assessed based on assignments and tests during the entire 15-week duration of their study. A component of the module assessment is a group assignment whereby students are required to complete a HAZOP study for a given section of a chemical processing plant.

Challenges Faced in Teaching and Learning HAZOP

Despite offering various advantages, HAZOP is not without its limitations. For example, it is well known for its time- and resource-intensive nature. Choy et al (2004) noted some of the challenges in conducting HAZOP exercises in academic settings:

- student difficulties in using all information they have acquired in several lecture courses and adapting to this qualitative assessment approach used in performing HAZOP Studies
- somewhat heavy and dry theory within the HAZOP lectures
- the absence of an absolute correct numerical answer to HAZOP is a difficult concept for students to appreciate

We would like to add that, from the student perspective, the difficulty in learning HAZOP stems from their lack of real-world practical experience operating large-scale chemical processing plant. A full-scale HAZOP process is very intensive and may takes several weeks, which does not fit well into a typical

engineering curriculum's timetable. As such, classroom HAZOP study often focused only on a selected section of a typical chemical plant to illustrate the methodology.

We tried using various pilot plants in our laboratories to simulate real-world HAZOP studies, but found that these are of limited effectiveness due to the pilot plants' much simpler configuration compared to real-world process equipment. Although rather well instrumented, our pilot plants still lack the kind of alarm and safety systems typically found in the chemical plants. Also, many of these pilot plants are designed to support specific core chemical engineering modules, and they are often operated quite independently of one another, lacking the close interaction between various process units in a chemical process plant. Furthermore, for safety reasons, there is also no practical way, in an academic setting such as in a laboratory or workshop, to provide students with the required experience in handling various process plant upsets for example high temperature or excessive over-pressure. In short, a real-world HAZOP environment simply cannot be replicated in an academic environment. Having a real-world multi-disciplinary team posed another problem. Whitty and Foord (2009) had highlighted the importance of good planning and having a knowledgeable team for the successful conduct of a HAZOP study. However, this is simply not possible among the students – there was no other diplomas that teaches their students HAZOP, such that they can form a team with our student!

We noted that students usually had no problem grasping the concepts in HAZOP, but faced great challenges in its application, and hence had serious concerns over the validity of the results of their HAZOP study. Our efforts at teaching HAZOP to students therefore focused on getting them to use critical thinking skills in applying the tools of the trade, supported by realistic practices in its applications through dynamic simulation of real-world chemical processes. We acknowledged that this may still represents a sub-optimal situation, as we recognized that we are still unable to address the multi-disciplinary team requirement of HAZOP. However, we believe that this will help alleviate some of the shortcomings identified earlier, and to this end, the changes we made are still beneficial to our students.

Using Dynamic Simulation for HAZOP Studies

Eikass et al (2005) advocated that using dynamic simulation has had a positive learning effect on substantial part of typical students in engineering programs. The advantages of using dynamic simulation for the chemical process industries had been nicely summed up by Dissinger (2008). Recently, a number of authors had reported on the use of dynamic simulation to aid in studying chemical process safety, for example in distillation operation (Werner et al, 2007), reactor design (Kowar and Pagone, 2001; Labovsky et al, 2007), flare minimization (Xu et al, 2009), plant start-up (Rutherford et al, 2003), etc. An excellent recent

summary of HAZOP and its evolution was provided by Dunjo et al (2010).

As noted previously, incorporating HAZOP into process safety education is a real challenge because the demonstration of the potential consequences of deviations from normal operating conditions is rather difficult, if not impossible. For example, it is inconceivable to create a real-world chemical reaction runaway just to demonstrate the consequence of such incident which include potential explosion! Combining HAZOP with dynamic simulation can provide the means for investigating those consequences in a safe environment. The use of dynamic simulation as a complement in the HAZOP study of chemical reactors has been suggested by Svandova et al (2005). Recently, Eizenberg et al (2006) reported the development of a "quantitative HAZOP" approach for safety education using mathematical modeling, demonstrating their procedures by applying it to a semi-batch reactor with exothermic reaction. Ramzan et al (2006) likewise combined dynamic simulation with HAZOP and referred to the framework as "Extended" HAZOP and later (Ramzan et al, 2007) illustrated its application using distillation as an example.

Initiative at Singapore Polytechnic

The team from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering decided in April 2009 to make use of dynamic simulation to support the teaching of HAZOP. We adopted the Kolb Learning Cycle as the basis of our theoretical approach. Briefly, Kolb's model has learners working through four phases, which are ideally iterative, as shown in Figure 1. Learners start by engaging in a situation (concrete experience, CE), then they observe their behavior and reflect on it (RO), from this, they generalize and develop abstract concepts (AC), which they then return to the field to test by applying them to new situations (AE).

Figure 1. Kolb's Cycle of Experiential Learning

Kolb's model has been used by many investigators. For example, Ulrich (1997) had noted the positive linkage between experiential learning and simulation and gaming. A study by Stice (1987) showed that the students' retention of knowledge increased from 20% to 90% when they were engaged in all four stages of learning. Herz and Merz (1998) used it to analyse

various studies to test whether economic simulation games support learning. Their empirical results indicated that simulation games support Kolb's four learning stages more efficiently than traditional teaching methods. Svinicki and Dixon (1987) extended the Kolb model and proposed instruction activities that support different aspects of the learning cycle. This is shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Instructional Activities for Kolb Cycle

CE	RO	AC	AE
Laboratories	Logs	Lectures	Simulations
Observations	Journals	Papers	Case studies
Simulations	Discussion	Model building	Laboratories
Games	Brainstorming	Projects	Field works
Field trips	Thought questions	Analogies	Projects
Trigger films	Rhetorical questions		
Problem sets			
Specific examples			

Moizer et al (2006), in their study of business simulations, noted that although simulations provide a useful vehicle for experiential learning, they do not automatically facilitate a high level of reflective observation. As such, these authors recommended that appropriate interventions are required on the part of the educator. And more recently, using control engineering tools, Abdulwahed et al (2008) demonstrated two important characteristics of the Kolb cycle: firstly, that it is stable and guarantees reaching the learning objectives, and secondly, that it is robust and can accommodate learner learning weakness through continuous process of the feedback loop repetition.

We hypothesize that dynamic simulation of chemical process plants, can also qualify as a "game", and hence can be used to improve our students' learning of HAZOP process. We have done two preliminary studies into students' receptiveness of using dynamic simulation as a learning tool in understanding process plant upsets. These two studies represented our initial attempt at providing concrete learning experience (CE, as per the Kolb Model) to our students. One of them, inculcation of critical thinking skills, had been covered by the author in the previous ISATE2009 symposium (Cheah and Phua, 2009). The study demonstrated that students in general were able to appreciate the relationship between various process variables such as flow rate, temperature, pressure, etc; and confirmed critical thinking as the area that posed the most difficulty among students. This present paper focus on validating the usefulness of dynamic simulation in helping students to better understand the HAZOP process, as well as gauging students' understanding of the interactions between different process equipment (e.g. failure of one equipment can affect another upstream or downstream equipment, or both) which is an integral part of HAZOP.

Description of Work Done

We did not adopt the approach of other investigators mentioned previously who used complex mathematical modeling to create our HAZOP model for various equipment. Instead, we make use of generic models from EnVision Systems (www.envisionsys.com), a commercial provider of dynamic simulation software packages for the training of process technicians. The EnVision Systems come with working models of various plant processes such as crude distillation unit, amine treating unit, acetylene conversion unit, etc.

For one thing, our students lacked mathematical modelling skills. Although arguably this can be taught, but this would require students to have various disciplinary knowledge in chemical engineering, some of which are not yet taught. More fundamentally, polytechnic education in Singapore needs to balance both fundamental chemical engineering sciences and practical hands-on skills. We therefore have to be mindful of our intended learning outcome of this initiative, and that is, to aid student apply the tools of HAZOP. Furthermore, as cautioned by Young et al (2007), one should not rush into building simulation models without a good understanding of the underlying engineering principles, as one may not even realized when an incorrect answer is produced. This is especially true for polytechnic education, where the level of fundamental know-how is being pegged at a level lower than that of university degree programs.

For Academic Year (AY) 2009/2010, the author designed two HAZOP assignments for the module *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention*, based on generic models available from EnVision Systems. One such model is the kettle reboiler system as shown in Figure 2. The other is based on the overhead condenser and accumulator system of a distillation column.

Figure 2. Kettle Reboiler for HAZOP Assignment

Students was given a brief write-up of the system under study, and are required to first complete their HAZOP assignment the usual way, i.e. using pen and paper. A week later, they are asked to complete the same exercise again, this time by running the EnVision System dynamic simulation program proper. The

exercises were implemented for two semesters in AY2009/2010. A total of four cohorts of students were involved, with key features as shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Characteristics of Students taking HAZOP – Part 1

Academic Year 2009				
Semester	1		2	
Student Cohort	Yr 2 Stage B	Yr 3 Stage A	Yr 2 Stage A	Yr 3 Stage B
Number of Students	63	65	55	61
Completed CPTC?	NO	YES	YES	YES

We took advantage of the change in course structure resulting from our adoption of the CDIO framework that resulted in the core module *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* being shifted from Year 3 to Year 2 (Cheah, 2008). Therefore, in AY2009/2010, there are two cohorts of students, one from Year 2 and another from Year 3, that were enrolled in the module. An interesting feature is that the Year 3 students had all completed a mandatory 6-week internship training at a live chemical processing plant located at the Chemical Process Technology Centre (CPTC) on Jurong Island while they were in their second year. Hence these Year 3 students have some prior plant operation knowledge before embark on the HAZOP assignment. On the other hand, one only group of the Year 2 students worked on the HAZOP assignment had completed their CPTC internship.

A short survey was conducted at the end of each assignment, using a 5-point Likert scale. Students are asked to indicate their learning experience on using dynamic simulation for HAZOP study, ranging from '1' for Strongly Disagree to '5' for Strongly Agree. Besides understanding of the HAZOP process, we also surveyed the students of other issues essential in the successful conduct of a HAZOP study, for example understanding the interaction between different equipment, ability to think critically, ability to integrate various knowledge from different chemical engineering disciplines in problem-solving. The survey questions are:

1. "I am better able to understand the objective of HAZOP."
2. "I am able to apply (and experience) the HAZOP analysis technique via hands-on with the simulator."
3. "I am more aware of the interconnectedness of various process variables (e.g. temperature, flow, pressure, level, etc) in a typical chemical plant."
4. "I am able to think more critically (e.g. analyze situations, predict outcomes, troubleshoot, etc) in attempting to account for the observed changes."
5. "I am more aware of the interconnectedness of various safety layers (e.g. control loops, trips,

process alarms, pressure relief systems, etc) in a typical chemical plant."

6. "I have a more holistic & integrated view of chemical engineering - i.e. I am able to link together various concepts learnt in different modules e.g. material balance, process instrumentation, process control, plant design, plant safety."

The following year, in AY2010/2011, we introduced a variation to the process. We used the previous two exercises (namely, one on the kettle reboiler, and another on the overhead condenser and accumulator system) as part of students' tutorial activities to enhance the CE component of the Kolb's cycle. They are then required to embark on a new dynamic simulation HAZOP assignment, using a more complicated depropanizer distillation system, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Depropanizer for HAZOP Assignment

A new set of survey was conducted, with changes in the questions as shown below: one open-ended question and five ranking questions using 5-point Likert scale ranging from '1' for Strongly Disagree to '5' for Strongly Agree.

1. "With dynamic simulation, I can better understand the interrelationships between different process variables (e.g. flow, temperature, etc) during a process upset."
2. "I am able to think more critically (e.g. analyze situation, predict outcome, troubleshoot, etc) in attempting to account for the observed changes during a process upset."
3. "The use dynamic simulation exercises have enhanced my understanding of a process upset and its possible consequences useful in HAZOP study."
4. "The various HAZOP exercises using dynamic simulation prior to the ICA had enhanced my ability to handle the HAZOP assignment in the ICA."
5. "I am able to use dynamic simulation to generate possible consequences of a process upset required in the HAZOP assignment in the ICA "
6. "List 2 factors that you think are **most challenging** to you in carrying out a HAZOP exercise."

At the time of this paper, one cohort of students (see Table 3) had completed the new HAZOP assignment.

Table 3
Characteristics of Students taking HAZOP – Part 2

Academic Year 2010		
Semester	1	2
Student Cohort	Year 2 Stage B	Year 2 Stage A
No of Students	66	Approx. 60
Completed CPTC?	NO	NO

Survey Results and Discussions of Learning Points

Survey results for academic years 2009 and 2010 are presented here in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively.

Table 4
Comparison of Student Responses – Part 1

Academic Year 2009/2010				
Semester	1		2	
Student Cohort	Year 2 Stage B	Year 3 Stage A	Year 2 Stage A	Year 3 Stage B
Assignment Average Mark	67.2	66.6	65.6	74.9
Question 1	3.98	3.90	3.88	4.02
Question 2	3.77	3.90	3.85	3.98
Question 3	3.95	3.96	3.96	4.13
Question 4	3.75	3.81	3.77	4.06
Question 5	3.91	3.86	3.85	4.02
Question 6	3.75	3.85	3.73	3.95

The results in Table 4 showed the Year 3 Stage B cohort performed slightly better overall. This can be attributed to the fact they are better calibre students to start with. On the other hand, the Year 3 Stage A cohort fared worse than the Year 2 Stage B cohort. Overall, the students in Year 2 are comparable in their capabilities, i.e. Stage A and Stage B showed no significant differences in academic achievements.

The performance of the Year 3 students taken as a whole seemed to suggest that having learnt more chemical engineering modules did not result in greater ability to conduct HAZOP studies compared to Year 2 students. This sounds plausible, considering the fact that in general students tend to compartmentalize their learning, largely due to the modular nature of teaching, leading to a lack of curriculum integration. This had resulted in students being unable to synthesize the knowledge gained from various modules into solving HAZOP problems. This is reflected in the relatively low score for Questions 5 and 6 which is related to thinking critically in predicting outcome of a HAZOP study, which requires an integrative view of chemical engineering knowledge.

Another interesting point is that live plant training at CPTC did not seem to help the Year 3 cohorts improve their HAZOP performance either. This may be attributed to the fact that HAZOP is not a training component at CPTC, and that the classroom HAZOP assignment bear no resemblance to the chemical plant in CPTC. This reflected the difficulty mentioned earlier about the teaching of HAZOP: it is virtually impossible to provide the necessary experience required in HAZOP study from an internship programme focusing on one aspect, albeit a major one, of chemical engineering; namely that of work competence.

Table 5
Comparison of Student Responses – Part 2

Academic Year 2010/2011		
Semester	1	2
Student Cohort	Year 2 Stage B	Year 2 Stage A
Assignment Average Mark	N.A.	N.A.
Question 1	3.96	N.A.
Question 2	4.00	N.A.
Question 3	3.91	N.A.
Question 4	3.78	N.A.
Question 5	3.85	N.A.

The results from Table 5 showed that although students generally are aware of the interconnectedness of various process variables (Question 1) and able to think more critically (Question 2), there is no significant improvements in students' learning of the HAZOP process using dynamic simulation (Questions 3 and 4). The 2 additional HAZOP exercises given to students prior to their assignment did not appear to enhance understanding their learning of HAZOP. This is evident from their answers to Question 6, of which a majority noted the major challenges being coming up probably causes of deviation of operating conditions from design intentions, and in predicting the consequences. At the time of this paper, the overall student performance is not yet available.

Due to unforeseen changes in manpower deployment, we were unable to introduce "active" RO component into the program, referring to concerted lecturer involvement in getting students to review their experience and thinking process. Due to time constraint and an already-packed curriculum, there is also no explicit teaching of critical thinking skills in the *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* module or any other modules in the diploma. Instead we only managed the usual – lecturer went through the solution in class. Any extra learning is left to occur outside the formal curriculum, at the students' own time and development. This is regrettable, as the Kolb's cycle emphasized the importance of the learner reflecting on his/her own learning. Reflections are now widely used ideas in many fields of learning, training and professional development. One reason for this is a growing

recognition within higher education of the important relationship between self-awareness and learning. In fact, Hillier (2002) went further to assert that:

Without critical reflection, teaching will remain at best uninformed, and at worst, ineffective, prejudiced and constraining.

Especially in our education system, active lecturer involvement is necessary to facilitate such reflective process among students, as the majority of them are unlikely able to manage the process on their own. However, reflective practice is not widely practiced by many of our existing lecturers, and it is probably true to say that many in fact lacked the skills in facilitating such processes with students. Although reflective practice is one of the key competencies in the training of new faculty, there is also a need to continually develop our existing lecturers through re-training and up-skilling. At the diploma level, we did engage in staff development in terms of action research and pedagogical development, but more on ad hoc basis. For example, we held regular sharing session and arranged for workshop when a new initiative was introduced. We need to be more proactive in developing our staff pedagogically.

Also at the institutional level, current practice in terms of annual curriculum review (both at the module and course level) had centered on student examination performance, technical content development. There is a lack of emphasis in the current review system on the need for lecturers to improve themselves pedagogically. Staff development programs are often handled separately from curriculum development as part of annual submission of training plan and budgets, which involved specifying broad training goals only.

Proposed Future Action Plans

We will need to increase the relevant concrete experience (CE) to our students from early in their study. There is no doubt for the need of the learner to be actively engaged in the learning process in order that they benefit from it. With regards to learning via dynamic simulation, we will start introducing dynamic simulation activities into our curriculum right from the first year itself. At this stage (Year 1), we will mainly focus on improving their understanding of the underlying chemical engineering principles, such as material and energy balances, vapor-liquid equilibrium, etc. These will be based on the chemical process models from EnVision Systems, so that students gain familiarity with the software at the same time as they learnt the various chemical engineering principles.

In Year 2, we will reinforce the learning process with activities to support CE; this time focusing on applying critical thinking skills in process troubleshooting, again via dynamic simulation exercises. These exercises will be derived from various

chemical processes used in the EnVision models so as to compensate for the students' lack of real plant experience. The dynamic simulation exercises will be introduced into various core chemical engineering modules, such as *Heat Transfer and Equipment* (heat exchanger fouling, tube leak), *Rotating Equipment* (pump deterioration, motor failure) and *Process Instrumentation* (valve malfunction, transmitter drift).

We will introduce elements of observation and reflection (RO) by first developing a suitable model on critical thinking appropriate for chemical process troubleshooting. We believed that a working model is very important to ensure that students understand the meaning of what we try to teach them, when we talked about critical thinking in the chemical engineering context. As noted by Kapranos (2007):

Unless they have a working model in their heads or are exposed to situations through which they can build such a model through their experiences, learning will not take place or it will be incomplete if it does. Of course it is important for students to know the facts, however, unless these facts can be put together in meaningful patterns they will not be of great use. Facts get their meaning from the way they fit into a particular context. When we speak to them of a good theory, we should be able to demonstrate to them how the various seemingly disparate facts of a topic are put together and make sense.

To support the above, we will increase the *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention* module's curriculum hours for from 45 to 60 hours. Besides covering some new topics and strengthening existing ones, the additional time will permit the explicit teaching of critical thinking skills needed in process troubleshooting and HAZOP study. Additional exercises will be designed for HAZOP study in this module. Students will also be required to submit an individual or group reflective journal that demonstrate the application of critical thinking in evaluating their thinking process during the conduct of the HAZOP assignment. This will then be reinforced in classroom discussions through facilitation by the lecturer. The goal is to help students build up competency in formulating abstract concepts of the inter-relationship of various equipment in a chemical processing plant, and develop generalization from skills learnt in one processing plant to another plant (AC). In terms of the Kolb's cycle, our approach can be represented in Figure 4.

Finally, in Year 3, we plan to expand the module *Process Control* to include optimization and troubleshooting, by raising its curriculum hours from 60 to 75 hours. HAZOP will be re-visited in this module, where students are expected to tackle more challenging assignments. We have already acquired more sophisticated dynamic simulation models such as the fairly complex catalytic hydrodesulfurization systems, and an amine treating system with one regenerator

servicing up to three separate absorbers in three different process units. Troubleshooting activities and HAZOP exercises will be developed based on these new models. At this stage, we expect the students to move on to the Active Experimentation (AE) stage of the cycle, and be able to demonstrate application of these troubleshooting skills in various exercises, as well as assessed on their performance in a HAZOP study for their plant design project.

Figure 4. Kolb's cycle reflecting the teaching of HAZOP in chemical engineering

In terms of implementation plan, this is shown schematically in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Plan for using Dynamic Simulation

And lastly, at the structural level, we are planning to introduce a "teaching and learning unit" to spearhead a more structured approach to faculty pedagogy development. Historically, getting a new lecturer up to speed with various demand of the job, which includes much administrative work on top of teaching takes priority over pedagogy. A new lecturer will be hard-pressed to learn and deliver the module contents, revise or prepare new PowerPoint slides, set examination questions, marking of scripts, etc. Pedagogy hence often took a backseat. Under this initiative, one or two experienced lecturer will be appointed as mentor to new lecturers to provide help and advice in carrying out curriculum re-design adopting a certain pedagogical approach. This will also formalized the ad hoc training

that we conducted in the past, and put faculty development in the forefront.

Conclusions

At the time of this paper, new dynamic simulation exercises were already completed for several core modules, for example, *Chemical Engineering Principles and Simulation* (Year 1), *Process Instrumentation* (Year 2), *Heat Transfer & Equipment* (Year 2) and *Separation Processes* (Year 3). Despite the best of intentions, there are still many processes that cannot be modeled for the lack of enough quantitative information, particularly in emergency situations. The number of available models from EnVision Systems is still limited. Use of dynamic simulation cannot and should not completely replace traditional teaching of HAZOP. Further research into students learning the HAZOP process using the approach outlined in this paper will help to validate the workability of the method.

More importantly, what started out as an effort to ease the teaching of HAZOP to students had opened up a whole new dimension in pedagogy development of lecturers, and helped to put into action plan a complete programme designed to develop both lecturers and students in their learning journey. We hoped to share our efforts in this area in the near future.

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